

RELATED RESEARCH IN MADRASAH EDUCATION IN THE PHILIPPINES: A LITERATURE REVIEW

Dr. Haipa Abdurahim-Salain

Basilan State College

Isabela City, Basilan, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7649096>

Published Date: 17-February-2023

Abstract: The Madrasah or Islamic education system in the Philippines provides the standard curriculum for elementary public schools and private Madaris. It aims to provide Muslim learners with appropriate and relevant educational opportunities while recognizing their cultural context and unique purposes for participating in the program offerings; and integrate content and competencies are relevant and of interest to Muslim learners (DO 41, s. 2017). The primal purpose of which is the preservation of the Islamic faith and culture in the Philippines. (Faisal, 2004 in Alag, 2013). This study reviewed related studies to understand the past, now and future of Madrasah Education in the Philippines. It elaborated the similarities and differences of these studies in terms of purpose, subjects/respondents, and research method.

Keywords: Education; Islamic; Madaris; Madrasah; Muslim; Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

As provided in DO 41, s. 2017, the Department of Education issued a policy on Madrasah Education Program (MEP) in the K to 12 Basic Education Program which aims to provide Muslim learners with appropriate and relevant educational opportunities while recognizing their cultural context and unique purposes for participating in the program offerings; and integrate content and competencies are relevant and of interest to Muslim learners. The MEP is to achieve that through the integration of the Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) in the regular basic education curriculum.

Department Order No. 40 (2011) provides that, the ALIVE for Grades 1 to 6 consists of two components: One, the Arabic language, and Islamic values, which is in addition to their regular subjects. This aims to develop the learners' functional literacy in Arabic that will enable them to read and understand the Holy Qur'an. Islamic values, the other component aims to help learners acquire the desired Islamic values that would guide them to Core Values of the Department. This will reinforce the realization of the just aspiration of Muslims in the country, especially in Mindanao, is to have an Islamic Education which is appropriate for the Bangsa Moro people. With the intension to produce generations of learned and intellectual Muslims imbued with Islamic values, it is recognized that the Madaris is an access to the Islamic education that they have longed for their youth.

Koul Lokesh (1984) declared that: "The review of related literature will give the researcher an understanding of the research methodology, It will help the researcher to know about the tools and instruments which proved to be useful and promoting in the previous study it also to provide insight in to the statistical methods through which validity of result is to be established". This review of related studies will promote a greater understanding of the problem of the study on madrasah education in the Philippines and its crucial aspects.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this article was to mainly present the past researches on Madrasah Education in the Philippines.

RELATED RESEARCHES

Madrasah Education In Zamboanga City As The Foundation Of The Muslim Way Of Life For Peaceful, Responsible, And Productive Citizen: Basis For 5-Year Strategic Development Plan (Jamaluddin and Cadir, 2017)

The Madrasah School is a very significant part of the Muslim community, it aimed to mold and develop the young and the community people as a whole and making them a loving, responsible and productive citizen. This study 'Madrasah Education In Zamboanga City As The Foundation Of The Muslim Way Of Life For Peaceful, Responsible, And Productive Citizen: Basis For 5-Year Strategic Development Plan', was conducted by Jamaluddin and Cadir (2017) aimed to identify the different issues and concerns of the madrasah schools and somehow give ideas based on the result found from the data gathered. This study aimed to address and answer the issues and status of the Madrasah Educational System in Zamboanga City district in terms of the following: 1. Organization and structure, the Site, Campus, Building, Offices and staff rooms. 2. Fiscal adequacy and capability 3. Faculty and development in terms of its Academic qualification, Professional performance, teaching assignment, Faculty development 4. Delivery and Classroom Management 5. Curriculum 6. Admission and 7. Issues and Problems. Also, what are the issues and problems besetting the madrasah education? Is there a significant difference in the status of the Madrasah schools when data are grouped according to the profiles of the school and the respondents? And what intervention program can be designed to enhance or improve the Madrasah schools?

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1) the status of the madrasah schools in Zamboanga city was found to be adequate and functioning well with some areas for improvement. 2) The issues and problems besetting the madrasah education, revealed that financial aspect is the major obstacle for sustainability of the madrasah in the Zamboanga City. From this problem emanates the issues on the lack of teaching and learning resources, minimal faculty development, non-standardized curriculum, no uniform admission policy and other problems. 3) Significant difference exists in the perception of the male and female respondents in terms campus, offices and staff rooms, and delivery & classroom management wherein the male's perception is higher than the female.

Likewise, significant difference was noted in the perception of the respondents in terms of age wherein those bracketed from ages 36 and above have lower ratings in the following areas namely; academic qualification, professional performance and faculty development. In terms of the year of service, there is no significant difference but in term of educational attainment based on foreign and local graduate teachers, there is significant difference in campus wherein foreign rated high while the locals rated "high" in academic requirements. On the other hand, in educational attainment in terms of whether the teacher is college of high school graduates, the college graduate teachers rated high in campus while the high school graduates rated "high" in academic requirements. Nevertheless, there is no significant difference in term of secular education.

Implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) in Marawi City, Philippines: Unveiling the Perceptions of ALIVE Teachers (Solaiman, 2017)

This study of Solaiman (2017) on the 'Implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) in Marawi City, Philippines: Unveiling the Perceptions of ALIVE Teachers' adopts the descriptive research design to gather information about the implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) and the prevailing conditions about the teaching of ALIVE in Marawi City, Philippines. A survey was made through questionnaires to assess the implementation of the teaching and the level of effectiveness of the implementation of ALIVE.

Findings had shown that there were no sufficient books and learning materials for ALIVE students. Hence, it is also recommended that provision for sufficient updated books and other references for every pupil, making the distribution 1:1 ratio be made. Likewise, the data depicted that there is a need to institute reforms on the hiring and in upgrading teacher qualification for them to be truly competent and highly skilled to deliver the goods to intended beneficiaries.

Therefore, it is deemed necessary that appointment of qualified and competent ALIVE teachers must be based on merit and fitness. In this vein, there is a need to make the qualifying exam for Arabic language an eligibility to get an employment item.

Furthermore, provision of scholarship program for ALIVE teachers should be made available. In the same manner that there is a need for the appointment of competent ALIVE supervisors, consultants or trainers in every district to oversee the program. Lastly as shown from the findings that the ALIVE program was not properly evaluated and monitored.

Thus, it is recommended that further study should be conducted to assess the needs of the ALIVE programs and may be an action plan might be proposed to the concerned authority to improve the effective and efficacious implementation of the ALIVE program.

Impact of the Implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) Program in the Philippines (Muhamat, 2015)

The Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) Program is the result of the dedicated efforts of the Department of Education Central, Regional and Division officials and Asatidz (teachers) who believe in the worth and development potential of every Muslim child in multicultural and diverse environment. The main objective of the study of Muhamat (2015) on the 'Impact of the Implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) Program in the Philippines', is to identify strategies towards national unity and harmony in Muslim-Christian relationship. The research methodology is in qualitative form with the method of interviews and contents analysis.

The results show education plays a vital role in honing set of beliefs towards a cultural change. Peace and development is achieved when a certain culture is satisfied especially when individual demand has been fulfilled.

A Comparative Study of Weekend Developmental Madrasah Curriculum in Davao City, Philippines (Deporos, 2015)

The study of Deporos (2015), 'A Comparative Study of Weekend Developmental Madrasah Curriculum in Davao City, Philippines', seeks to understand and describe the implementation of Weekend Developmental Madrasah in Davao City ran by the Comprehensive Madrasah Development and Promotion program. It focuses the totality of its curriculum and find out the best answer of the following questions: (1) What are the similarities and differences of several madrasah curricula under comprehensive program? (2) How the teachers understand about curriculum? (3) What are the cause of unimplemented unification of curriculum?

The Descriptive-Qualitative research method was used in this study in which inductive as part of its approaches. To answer the questions mentioned above, basically the guidelines book will be measured provided by the madrasah comprehensive development and promotion program. The findings of the study were:

With the standard curriculum formed by the Madrasah Comprehensive Development and Promotion Program and the implementation of its standards it shows from data that each schools haven't meet the desire program to be implemented by the office. Each school don't have proper source or foundation for their implementation.

The Curriculum implementation of the standard given from the Madrasah Comprehensive Development and Promotion Program was not applied and each weekend madrasah facing difficulty with huge needs in terms of physicality of schools. Proper guidelines and procedures to be applied each from time to time. According to the researcher's survey. No school visitation, no evaluation and basically no progress in terms of system's development.

Evaluation of Madrasah Education in Elementary Schools of Digos City (Alag, 2013)

This study on evaluation of Madrasah Education in elementary schools of Digos City was conducted by Alag (2013), to determine the demographic profile of Asatidz, the problems met in their respective Madrasah and their curriculum implementation. To measure the Asatidz competency level in teaching Arabic Language and Islamic Values, the tool used was taken from Curriculum Management Assessment Data culled from the fourth domain of the Philippine National Competency-Based Teacher Standard (NCBTS).

The Descriptive-correlational method was used in this study. The results of responses coming from all Asatidz in nine (9) Madaris of Digos City were used in the analysis using the frequency, mean, standard deviation, and Pearson r.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp: (88-91), Month: January - February 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Results of the study disclosed that there was no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the Asatidz and the extent of their Madrasah curriculum implementation. Also, on the extent of the problems met by the Asatidz and the extent of their Madrasah curriculum implementation did not show a significant relationship. However, on educational attainment, there was a highly significant relationship in the implementation of Madrasah curriculum. It is recommended that the DepEd must design policies that will provide more education trainings for Asatidz to become more capable of helping students to acquire the competencies needed to evolve today.

III. SYNTHESIS

In terms of purpose, there were similarities between the studies of: Solaiman (2017) on the 'Implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) in Marawi City, Philippines: Unveiling the Perceptions of ALIVE Teachers', which was to gather information about the implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) and the prevailing conditions about the teaching of ALIVE in Marawi City, Philippines; Muhamat (2015) on the 'Impact of the Implementation of Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) Program in the Philippines'; Deporos (2015), 'A Comparative Study of Weekend Developmental Madrasah Curriculum in Davao City, Philippines', which sought to understand and describe the implementation of Weekend Developmental Madrasah in Davao City ran by the Comprehensive Madrasah Development and Promotion program; and Alag (2013), on the 'Evaluation of Madrasah Education in Elementary Schools of Digos City', to determine the demographic profile of Asatidz, the problems met in their respective Madrasah and their curriculum implementation.

In terms of subjects, similar sets – the ALIVE teachers in public elementary schools, were observed, such as the studies of: Solaiman (2017), which subjects were ALIVE teachers in elementary schools in Marawi City Division; Muhamat (2015), which also had ALIVE staff and teachers as subjects; Deporos (2015), which also had ALIVE teachers as subjects; and Alag (2013), with Asatidz (teachers) as her subjects; and Jamaluddin and Cadir (2017), which also had teachers as subjects in their study.

In terms of research method, the Descriptive-Quantitative research method used by Solaiman (2017), differs with those of Deporos (2015) and Muhamat (2015), which used the Descriptive-Qualitative research method. Also, different was the Descriptive-Correlational method adopted by Alag (2013) which determined the significant relationship between the demographic profile of Asatidz and the extent of their Madrasah Curriculum implementation, and the significant relationship between the extent of the problems encountered by the Asatidz and the extent of their Madrasah Curriculum implementation.

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